

INNOVATIVE TRENDS AND TECHNOLOGIES IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Modern realities require changes in all spheres of human life. Education is no exception. The development of the education system requires the study and implementation of new teaching methods. General processes in society, global problems - all this is associated with the need to implement innovations. The relevance of the study of this topic is due to the modernization of education, where one of the most important areas is the quality of knowledge.

A modern foreign language lesson requires the use of innovative technologies that ensure increased efficiency of the educational process, guaranteeing the achievement of planned learning outcomes. Interactive learning is a special form of organizing cognitive activity, which consists of ensuring constant active interaction and is based on dialogue, modeling the situation of the product, and a free exchange of opinions. This is mutual learning, in which both students and the teacher are equal subjects of learning, with the only difference being that the teacher becomes a real leader of the student body, the organizer of the learning process.

The article discusses innovative trends and technologies that influence English language teaching. It focuses on the use of artificial intelligence, digital platforms and gaming technologies. It describes the benefits and challenges associated with the introduction of new technologies into the learning process.

In the digital age, English language teaching is undergoing significant changes. The development of artificial intelligence, mobile applications and virtual reality creates new opportunities and challenges for students and teachers. The purpose of this article is to describe the key technologies and trends influencing modern English language teaching.

A creative teacher has broad opportunities and an unlimited field for innovative activity, since in practice he can experiment and verify the effectiveness of various teaching methods, adjust them, carry out detailed structuring of research into the educational process, and propose new technologies and teaching methods. The main condition for such activity is the innovative potential of the teacher. The innovative potential of a teacher is a set of socio-cultural and creative characteristics of the personality of a teacher who demonstrates a willingness to improve pedagogical activity, the presence of internal means and methods capable of ensuring this willingness. [1].

The process of reforming modern education involves ensuring high-quality subject training of specialists in the context of reducing classroom workload and increasing information. One of the ways to solve this problem is to introduce new, more effective methods and technologies of training. These include electronic learning (e-learning), distance learning technologies.

In the conditions of developmental learning, it is necessary to achieve maximum activity of students, which is ensured by interactive teaching methods. Unlike active methods, interactive methods are focused on broader interaction of students not only with the teacher, but also with each other and on the dominance of student activity in the learning process. [2].

Interactive learning is learning in a dialogue mode, during which the participants of the pedagogical process interact with the aim of mutual understanding, joint solution of educational tasks, development of personal qualities of students.

Educational material is easier to learn and is stored in memory for the longest time when the student does not passively perceive what the teacher says, but actively acts when studying the material.

It should be noted that high-quality training of students would be impossible without the use of modern educational technologies. Innovative methods of teaching foreign languages, which are based on the direction and development and self-improvement of the individual, on the disclosure of his creative potential, create the prerequisites for the effective improvement of the educational process in higher educational institutions. These technologies help to implement a personality-oriented approach to teaching, provide individualization and differentiation of training taking into account the abilities of children, their level of knowledge.

Interactive learning technologies are considered as ways of acquiring knowledge, developing skills and abilities in the process of learning a foreign language and interaction between a teacher and students as subjects of educational activity.

Key technologies:

1. Artificial intelligence:

– AI technologies such as chatbots and virtual assistants (e.g. Duolingo or Grammarly) enable a personalized approach to learning.

2. Virtual and augmented reality (VR/AR):

– Virtual environments such as VRChat for speaking practice or learning simulations.

3. Mobile apps:

– Apps such as Quizlet and Memrise for vocabulary development and quizzes. [3].

Innovative technologies make learning more accessible and interactive, but there are challenges with start-up costs and teacher training.

To solve educational tasks, the teacher uses the following interactive forms:

- case technologies;
- "round table";
- debates;
- business games;
- case-study;
- trainings;
- video conferences;
- "brainstorming";
- focus groups;
- role-playing games;
- group discussions;
- project method. [4].

To increase the effectiveness of the educational process when conducting English lessons, I most often use the following pedagogical technologies: project methodology, research activities, information and communication technologies, and gaming technologies.

Modern communicative methodology offers wide implementation of active non-standard methods and forms of work in the educational process for better conscious assimilation of the material.

As practice shows, the following forms of work are very effective: individual, pair, group and team work.

The most famous forms of pair and group work:

- internal (external) circles (inside/outside circles);
- brainstorming;
- jigsaw reading;
- exchange of opinions (think-pair-share);
- pair interviews (pair-interviews) and others. [5].

The analysis of the practice of teaching English in higher education institutions showed that textbooks and methodological developments used in the learning process do not sufficiently take into account the role and importance of students' motivational sphere and the nature of the relationship between motivational readiness to acquire knowledge. Therefore, the current problem is to study the motivational sphere of students, develop ways and methods of its correction and development.

The leading motives for studying English as a professional discipline by students of higher education institutions are the motives of professional personal development. The innovative status of a foreign language teacher in the system of developmental learning gives him freedom of action in methodological and didactic activities. [6].

Thus, we can conclude that the effectiveness of communicatively oriented teaching of foreign languages in higher education institutions will depend on the desire and ability of teachers to use the positive experience of domestic and foreign scientists and practitioners in the humanistic approach to teaching. Methods of teaching foreign languages, which are based on the humanistic approach, help to reveal the creative potential of students and contribute to the development and self-improvement of the educational and communicative process.

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